

LIQUID COMPOSITE MOULDING OF ANIONICALLY POLYMERISED POLYAMIDE 12.

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SUMMARY

Mainly two types of processing routes have been developed to transform thermoplastic polymers into final composite products using: a) polymerised products such as powder, films or preimpregnated preforms and b) monomers to be transformed to polymer in-situ during the process. The low initial viscosity of monomer systems can drastically reduce the time and the pressure needed for the impregnation of the reinforcement while polymer flow can further be optimised for complex-shaped parts. The impregnation is followed by the polymerisation of the monomers and the cooling of the obtained parts. Currently, researcher and engineers are very active in the development of novel material systems for even faster polymerisation and improved processing ability.

The polymerisation mechanisms of a novel anionically polymerised polyamide 12 was studied in details leading to models and experimental validation of reaction kinetics and viscosity evolution. The results were applied to the building of a reaction injection pultrusion process and of a thermoplastic resin transfer moulding process. For the later, the infiltration process was studied in details as it was determined by the flow of the liquid monomer through a complex woven fibre architecture and by the removal of voids from the reinforcement and the mould cavity. Matrix flow properties and reinforcement permeability were determined while composite parts were produced under different flow conditions in order to assess the formation and transport of voids in such a reactive thermoplastic system.

Results correlated the final macro-and micro-void content of the composite to the capillary numbers specific to each processing condition. By this approach, optimum flow conditions were determined to minimise void content during liquid moulding of the studied thermoplastic composite. Models, processing windows and engineering tools are currently developed as it is clear today that the liquid moulding of thermoplastic composites has all the potentials to undergo rapid development and implementation.

KEYWORDS: Reactive, Thermoplastic, Liquid moulding, Composites, Void

INTRODUCTION

Thermoplastic polymers exhibit good properties such as high impact strength, high service temperature, ease of storage and potential for repair, which make them appealing candidates for composite matrices. However, due to their relatively high viscosity, a major challenge with thermoplastic composites is to minimise their process cycle times while optimising consolidation quality. Several thermoplastic systems bring new potentials for rapid processing of thermoplastic composites^[1]. The Anionic activated Polymerisation of Lactam 12 (APLC 12), a recently developed system patented by EMS-Chemie, is used here to investigate different processing routes based on liquid moulding of thermoplastic composites. Benefiting from its very low viscosity (on the order of mPa/s), the Lactam 12 monomer is mixed with activator/initiator system prior to be injected in a fibre preform where polymerisation occurs in-situ, resulting in a Polyamide 12 matrix.

The polymerisation mechanisms of APLC 12 were studied in details leading to models and experimental validation of reaction kinetics and viscosity evolution^[2-5]. The results were applied to the building of a reaction injection pultrusion process^[6] and of a reactive thermoplastic resin transfer moulding process^[7, 8].

In liquid composite moulding, the reinforcement becomes impregnated during the moulding process. Hence the risks for void formation is generally greater than in competing composite manufacturing processes based on pre-impregnated materials. Void formation has been widely investigated in the case of thermoset resin transfer moulding (RTM)^[9-33]. These studies pointed out causes of void formation to include the diffusion of gases in the resin during storage, mechanical air entrapment during infiltration, nucleation of voids due to chemical reaction between the resin and the reinforcement or the release agent, leakage of the mould, inhomogeneities in the reinforcement. These phenomena resulted in different types of voids such as dry spots (large un-impregnated zones), macroscopic voids (entrapped air during the infiltration process), microscopic voids (incompletely infiltrated bundles), voids created by moisture or gas liberation in the resin, or voids created by cavitation due to resin shrinkage.

One of the main focuses in liquid composite moulding is infiltration. Indeed, resin flow takes place at two scales: the macro-flow occurs in-between fibre bundles and is driven by the hydrodynamic pressure gradient induced by the applied injection pressure, whereas micro-flow occurs inside the channels and is mainly lead by capillary pressure. As demonstrated in numerous studies on thermoset RTM^[10, 21, 24, 30, 31, 34-38], if these pressure gradients are not balanced, micro- and macro- flows have different infiltration velocities and air entrapment is likely to occur. This balance between hydrodynamic pressure and capillarity depends on liquid properties, pressure profile, and reinforcement structure. The capillary number (Ca) can be used to give the measure of the ratio of the viscous and the capillary forces in the flow field:

$$Ca = \frac{\eta \cdot u_s}{\gamma_{LV}} \quad \text{Equation 1}$$

where η is the viscosity of liquid, u_s is the superficial velocity, and γ_{LV} is the surface tension of the liquid.

The causes of void formation in composites based on liquid moulding of reactive thermoplastics. Have not yet been investigated in details, even though a rather high void content is found in plates processed in “normal conditions”. The present articles aims to propose routes for the minimum of void in reactive composite moulding with a main focus on the diffusion of gas into the monomer, on the infiltration process and on the matrix shrinkage.

MATERIALS

In the reactive thermoplastic system considered here, the new liquid activating system contains both activator and catalyst^[39]. The monomer is stored above its melting temperature, 154°C, under a Nitrogen environment preventing degradation. The liquid activator is stored at room temperature, also under Nitrogen. Stored separately, these reactants have an infinite shelf life.

The system consists of a cyclic amide monomer (Lauro lactam), which polymerises in-situ, into polyamide 12 via an anionic ring-opening reaction. The polymerisation is initiated after the impregnation of the fibre bed by the activated monomer.

The first step of the anionic polymerisation is the formation of a Lactam anion, which becomes the initiator required for the propagation reaction. When only the Lactam and its anion are used, polymerisation proceeds slowly. When activators are added, here N-acyllactam structures, polymerisation can be completed within minutes. Initiators form growth centres and hence the type and concentration of initiator and activator together with the temperature influence polymerisation kinetics and final molecular weights. Polymerisation is sensitive to both the purity of the compounds and the presence of moisture, oxygen and other products such as amines and acids^[2, 3, 40].

Tenax 5N21 carbon fibres were used, arranged in a 5-harness satin weave of 440 g/m².

The thermoplastic liquid composite moulding process consists essentially in the following steps. The molten monomer and liquid activator are pumped separately to a mixing head connected to the mould to enable injection of activated monomer, see *Fig. 1*. The mould contains a reinforcement preform through which infiltration occurs. All the process is run at a minimum of 175°C. After complete polymerisation, the mould is cooled down, enabling solidification and crystallisation of the polyamide 12 matrix.

Fig. 1: Schema of the injection unit

EXPERIMENTAL AND RESULTS

Diffusion of Nitrogen.

As the monomer is molten and continuously stored under Nitrogen, this gas can dissolve in the future matrix and subsequently initiate voids. The diffusion coefficient of Nitrogen gas in molten Lactam D_{La} is required to approximate the quantity of gas present in the monomer. Based on the work of Lunström^[18] who studied diffusion of air in vinyl ester, two experimental set-ups were developed to approximate the diffusion coefficient of Nitrogen in molten Lactam. Fick's second law was solved for these two geometries. The first geometry (see *Fig. 2*) enabled to approximate the product $\sqrt{D_{La}} \cdot H$, where H is Henry's constant, considering *diffusion through an infinite surface*. The second approach (*Fig. 3*)

considered *diffusion from a gas bubble into the bulk* and enabled to approximate the product $D_{La} \cdot H$. Both methods are required to determine the value of D_{La} .

Fig. 2: Diffusion through an infinite surface, with (1) silicon drop; (2) capillary tube, section S_1 ; (3) Schematic Nitrogen molecules; (4) Silicon plug; (5) Glass beaker, section S_0 ; (6) Molten Lactam

Fig. 3: Diffusion from a gas bubble into the bulk, with: (1) Syringe containing Nitrogen gas; (2) Hollow flexible tube; (3) Chimney enabling filling of molten Lactam; (4) Glass plate closing tight the beaker; (5) Glass beaker; (6) Molten Lactam; (7) Nitrogen bubble injected in the beaker

a) Diffusion through an infinite surface

Experiments were run with molten Lactam degassed at two different pressures, 10 and 100 mbars. As shown in Fig. 4, the slope slightly differs, and leads to different values for $\sqrt{D_{La}} \cdot H$. Theoretically, this product should not depend on the degassing pressure for an isothermal experiment. However, the temperature could vary by three degrees around the set temperature of 175°C. Additionally, the degassing pressure slightly varied during the degassing operation, which can lead to scattering in the results. Results are presented in Table 1.

Fig. 4: Displacement $\delta l = l_0 - l_1$ of the silicon drop vs time

Degassing pressure	Slope	$\sqrt{D_{La}} \cdot H$
10 mbars	0.025	$6,10 \cdot 10^{-10}$
100 mbars	0.1	$2,68 \cdot 10^{-09}$

Table 1: Results of diffusion through an infinite surface

b) Diffusion from a gas bubble into the bulk

Lactam samples were carefully degassed for more than two hours. As shown in Fig. 5, two experiments were run, enabling approximation of $D_{La} \cdot H$ as shown in Table 2.

Slope	$D_{La} \cdot H$
$2,95 \cdot 10^{-8}$	$1,16 \cdot 10^{-13}$
$4,25 \cdot 10^{-8}$	$1,67 \cdot 10^{-13}$

Table 2: Results of a bubble diffusing in the bulk

Fig. 5: Evolution of bubble radius R_v versus time

Grouping results from these two experiments enables to approximate the diffusion coefficient of Nitrogen in molten Lactam at 175°C. It has to be noted that these results are from preliminary study and exhibited some scatter. Hence, the coefficient obtained should be carefully considered, and is between the following boundaries: $1,9 \cdot 10^{-9} \text{ m}^2 \cdot \text{sec}^{-1} < D_{La} < 7,49 \cdot 10^{-8} \text{ m}^2 \cdot \text{sec}^{-1}$.

Air entrapment during infiltration

A mould was developed enabling the visualisation of the flow front during infiltration of fibres by the activated monomer (Fig. 6), and was used to process APLC 12 composites at different injection velocities, thus various capillary numbers. Sections of the obtained plates ($170 \times 230 \text{ mm}^2$) were analysed under a microscope, and the void content was quantified by image analysis.

Fig. 6 : Infiltration set-up, with: (1) Inlet for activated Lactam 12; (2) High accuracy pressure transducer; (3) Heated mould; (4) Compressed air inflating hoses to close the mould; (5) Heat regulation system; (6) Computer + acquisition system to monitor pressure and temperature vs time

During an injection in the mould significant capillary effects were highlighted, as shown in Fig. 7: a clear wicking flow is observed in the fibre bundles.

Fig. 7 : Photography showing the strong wetting of carbon fibre bundles by the activated Lactam

The influence of the balance between viscous and capillary pressure on final composite porosity was determined in injecting at different velocities. This is represented in *Fig. 8*, where the void content is plotted for different capillary numbers.

Fig. 8 : Void content evolution versus infiltration velocity

The void content ranges between 6 and 18% and shows a minimum in the range of $Ca=6,5 \cdot 10^{-3}$. Below this critical velocity, the void content increases significantly with decreasing Ca, whereas above this critical velocity, the tendency is that void content increases slightly with increasing velocity.

Voids observed qualitatively differed, depending on the injection velocity. Indeed, voids observed in plates made at injection velocities corresponding to Ca below the critical Ca were mainly large voids located in inter-bundles zones, as shown in *Fig. 9*. Conversely, in plates produced at velocities corresponding to Ca above the critical Ca voids located inside the bundle were mainly observed, see *Fig. 10*.

Fig. 9: Macro void in inter-bundle areas

Fig. 10: Micro voids inside the bundles

Matrix shrinkage

No shrinkage was observed during polymerisation, but this was not true upon cooling. Indeed, Polyamide 12 being a semi-crystalline polymer, a fraction of the material will crystallise upon cooling below Polyamide 12 melting temperature (174°C), while the amorphous fraction will solidify below the glass transition temperature (40°C). The shrinkage was quantified for different polymerisation conditions, as well as for different cooling conditions listed in Table 3. The volume shrinkage was measured in a test-tube by the following method: as soon as the polymer started to solidify, a known amount of silicon oil was injected in the test tube. Reading the level of oil enabled calculation of the polymer volume as a function of time.

<i>Influence of cooling rate</i>		
<i>% liq. act. system</i>	2.5	2.5
<i>Cooling time from 180°C to <40°C</i>	25 min	100 min
<i>Shrinkage %</i>	8.6	9.3

Table 3: Effect of cooling conditions on solidification shrinkage

<i>Influence of activator to monomer percentage</i>			
<i>La-12 volume</i>	7.7	7.7	7.7
<i>% liq. act. system</i>	1.5	5	9
<i>Liq. act. system volume (mL)</i>	0.1	0.4	0.7
<i>Shrinkage % (on total vol.)</i>	9.0	8.6	8.3

Table 4: Effect of liq. act. system to monomer percentage on solidification shrinkage

It resulted that at low cooling rate an homogeneously distributed shrinkage occurred (9.3%), whereas at high cooling rate a large shrinkage was observed, mainly at the top of the sample, resulting in a 8.6% shrinkage. By increasing the liquid activating system to Lactam ratio, a decrease in total shrinkage was measured. It is to note that when shrinkage is calculated based on Lactam volume used (not accounting for added liquid activating system volume) the shrinkage content obtained, 9.1%, is independently of the percentage of liquid activating system added.

DISCUSSION

Liquid moulding of APLC 12 was successfully performed for the processing of several composite plates. Different processing conditions were used to study void formation and types in this reactive thermoplastic composite. Voids were observed at the entrance of the mould. The use of different mixing head geometries previously indicated that it was not the mixing head which generated voids. As the monomer granules are molten and stored under Nitrogen, it is worth considering this effect.

Diffusion of Nitrogen

The diffusion coefficient of Nitrogen in molten Lactam at 170°C was experimentally determined to be approximately $D_{La} = 7,35 \cdot 10^{-9} \text{ m}^2 \cdot \text{sec}^{-1}$. As a comparison, the diffusion coefficient obtained by Lundstöm^[18] when studying diffusion of air in vinylester was estimated to $8 \cdot 10^{-12} \text{ m}^2 \cdot \text{sec}^{-1}$, that is 3 orders of magnitude lower. The viscosity of Lactam is 300 times lower than the viscosity of the vinylester considered, and the temperature is much higher in the case of Lactam (175° instead of 20°C). These both factors will tend to promote diffusion, as observed in Einstein formula^[41, 42]:

$$D = \frac{K \cdot T}{6 \cdot \pi \cdot \eta \cdot a} \quad \text{Equation 2}$$

where K is Boltzmann constant, T the temperature, η the viscosity and a the diffusing particle diameter. Based on the approximated diffusion coefficient obtained, we can assume that diffusion of Nitrogen in molten Lactam will have significant effects.

The significant difference in the diffusion coefficient highlights that Nitrogen will diffuse much faster in Lactam than air in vinylester. Moreover, in thermoset liquid composite moulding the resin is degassed before injection, significantly decreasing the diffused gas content in the resin, whereas Lactam monomer is melted and stored in the tank under Nitrogen atmosphere, for stability reason. Additionally, injection pressure in thermoset liquid composite moulding is commonly in the range of 5-35 bars, as compared with less than 1 bar for APLC 12 processing. Gathering all this considerations led to the conclusion that a

potential source of voids in APLC 12 processing arises from the amount of dissolved Nitrogen in the monomer, which could produce bubbles as T increases. Indeed, at higher temperatures, gas volume expands, and also the concentration at saturation decreases, resulting in void formation. Currently, this diffusion coefficient is used to study the reduction of void diameter when flushing the reinforcement with degassed monomer.

Infiltration

As shown in *Fig. 8* the infiltration velocity influenced void formation both quantitatively (void content) and qualitatively (void size and location), see *Fig. 9* and *Fig. 10*. This is explained by the unbalance of viscous and hydrostatic forces. The capillary number is used to quantify the ratio of hydrostatic to viscous forces. Below the critical capillary number, the capillary effects dominate and lead to gas entrapment in the inter-bundles spaces *Fig. 10*, whereas above the critical capillary number, total infiltration of the fibre bundles is not achieved, resulting in micro-porosities inside fibre bundles. These observations on the considered thermoplastic correlate well with previous works on thermoset infiltration that led to the same conclusions ^[10, 21, 24, 30, 31, 34-38].

In APLC 12 infiltration, a tendency showed that a minimum void content was obtained in the range of $Ca=6,5 \cdot 10^{-3}$. Patel observed minimum void contents for capillary numbers in the range of 1 to $5 \cdot 10^{-3}$ depending on the infiltrating liquid used^[28]. Indeed, Patel highlighted the influence of an additional parameter to account for, namely the contact angle. The relationship between void formation and capillary number can be improved when the capillary number is divided by the contact angle, hence defining a modified capillary number Ca^* as:

$$Ca^* = \frac{\eta \cdot u_s}{\gamma_{LV} \cdot \cos \theta} \quad \text{Equation 3}$$

Patel, Rohatgi and James Lee ^[26, 28, 32] used the modified capillary number as they noticed that the critical Ca varied depending on the liquid used. They observed that the flow led by capillary pressure (low flow rate) resulted in macro-voids located in the inter-bundle area, whereas flow led by hydrodynamic pressure resulted in poor wetting, that is micro-voids inside the fibre bundles, in the interstices between the fibres. They noticed that above a certain critical flow velocity, no macro-voids were formed. Below this critical velocity the void fraction increased logarithmically. They observed different critical velocities for different liquids, showing that void fraction was not only a function of injection velocity, but also depended on the liquid properties.

So far the contact angle of Lactam is not determined, but the contact angle of comparable materials varies from 10 to 35°. Hence, minimum void content is obtained for Lactam infiltrating carbon fibres in the range: $6,6 \cdot 10^{-3} < Ca^* < 7,9 \cdot 10^{-3}$ which is exactly in the range of the critical Ca found in the present work. This is slightly different from the range of $5 \cdot 10^{-4}$ to 10^{-3} obtained by Patel^[26, 28] on oil, water, ethylene glycol and unsaturated polyester resin, but it shows the same trend. The difference in critical modified capillary number can be explained by the dependence of contact angle on velocity, resin viscosity and surface tension. The dependence of contact angle on capillary number has been reported elsewhere^[43] as beginning in the range of $10^{-6} < Ca < 10^{-5}$. To account for this effect, Patel et al.^[44] replaced $\cos \theta$ in Equation 3 by $T[\theta]$, which is a geometric factor for the contact angle of the liquid-air interface passing through the pore. However, he concluded that the resin systems used in LCM applications have surface tension values similar to each other, thus approximation of $T[\theta]$ by $\cos \theta$ is acceptable.

Shrinkage

A second particular characteristic observed in our experiments (*Fig. 5*) is a relatively high “minimum void content” ($X_v = 6\%$), highlighting that if infiltration is a major issue in liquid composite moulding, other parameters have to be controlled to ensure low void content in liquid moulded composites. Gas diffusing in the molten monomer stored in the tank can also generate porosity in the final component as previously explained. Shrinkage is the other cause for residual porosity in composites. Indeed, it was

approximately 9% shrinkage occurred upon cooling from processing temperature (180°C) down to room temperature. In our case, with a reinforcement volume fraction of 46% shrinkage can account for approximately 5% of the total void content in the composite.

CONCLUSIONS

Different origins for void formation in reactive thermoplastic composites were investigated for APLC 12 composites. To minimise void formation the following solutions are proposed:

- Degas the monomer while melting it, and keep degassing molten Lactam during storage,
- Inject at velocities close to the determined critical capillary number in order to minimise gas entrapment during infiltration,
- Complete the process by a slight compression of the mould during cooling in order to compensate for crystallisation shrinkage.

The study provided a better definition of the processing windows for liquid moulding of thermoplastic composites.

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